

Implementation of Bluetooth Enabled Home Automation System

Cookey Iyen

Department of Pure and Applied Physics, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Benedict Ayomanor

Department of Science Laboratory Technology, University of Petroleum resources Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria

Dafa Orseer

Department of Pure and Applied Physics, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Iyen, C., Ayomanor, B. & Orseer, D. (2024). Implementation of Bluetooth Enabled Home Automation System. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 310-318.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(2\).27](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(2).27)

Abstract:

Home automation is becoming more and more popular as a concept because it increases productivity by lowering human oversight and labor. Home automation systems allow us to operate a variety of gadgets, including air conditioners, TVs, fans, lights, and more. Furthermore, additional functions like emergency systems, security, alarms, etc. may be incorporated into home automation systems. There are numerous varieties of home automation technologies, including those that are controlled via Bluetooth, the Internet, RF, infrared, and other remotes. Each type comes with its own benefits

and drawbacks. For this research, we have programmed and constructed a Bluetooth-controlled home automation device using a Bluetooth-enabled Android phone. The designed device is able to switch enabled home appliances within a 100-meter radius of the phone.

Keywords: *Home Automation, Bluetooth, Smart home, Arduino, Electronics, Mobile Technology.*

Introduction

We are currently in a time of rapid technological growth when science and technological gadgets are now within the reach of most of the inhabitants of the planet in the form of mobile phones, tablets, laptops, and computers. Automation is the utmost desire of man, in which most works done by man can be carried out completely independently by machines or with minimal inputs from humans. Automation has been implemented in many areas of life that were formerly fully manually performed, such as agriculture, manufacturing, security, and others. However, a home, being a place where people stay, rest, and relax, can also be made more convenient and comfortable by introducing

some automation features to limit human physical efforts in controlling gadgets in the home. One of the main areas is the switching of electronic circuits. In which people have to move around the house locating switches and switching them on and off, irrespective of how tired or physically incapacitated they are. The mobile phone is the most convenient device to serve as a means of control for most of the gadgets in the house. According to research on the population of the world, which stands at above 8.01 billion (UNICEF, 2023) the present population of people worldwide who use smartphones has grown to 6.93 billion, corresponding to 86.5% of the global populace having a smartphone. This number has risen significantly from 2016, when there were just

3.668 billion users, or 49.40% of the worldwide population for that year (Turner, 2024). Also, most people are always in possession of their mobile phones, which makes it a very good option to exploit for wirelessly switching household gadgets.

Home automation is an umbrella term used to describe the use of specific automation techniques in private homes for enhanced convenience, comfort, energy efficiency, and security. It includes the capacity to perform operations automatically and remotely monitor or alter the status of electrical and electronic devices connected either locally or through the internet. Its purpose is to make the house more secure and comfortable. It is a collection of devices that can automate a house. Thus, time is saved and human labor is reduced while home efficiency is increased. Home automation also involves the control of some gadgets that would otherwise only be controlled manually, such as doors and windows (Vijayarangam et al., 2022; de Jong et al., 2022; Brahimi, 2021; VJ, 2021; Dorve et al., 2019; Kshirsagar et al., 2020).

Bluetooth is a protocol for wireless information transfer among gadgets that are situated in close proximity to one another. It is capable of carrying out data transmission and reception simultaneously. It is regarded as a low-power short-range radio technology for interconnecting devices and can be used in building short-range personal area networks (PANs). It is founded on the IEEE 802.15.1 benchmark. It is a widely used technology in data transfer between phones and other gadgets, listening to music, and remotely picking up calls using the Bluetooth-enabled headset connected to the phone (Oprea and Mo- canu, 2021; He et al., 2021; Lounis and Zulkernine, 2019; Long, 2021; Juturu et al., 2020). Bluetooth transmits information or data among stationary or mobile gadgets through the unofficial ISM frequency spectrum of the bandwidth 2.4 GHz to 2.485 GHz (Suryavanshi et al., 2019). It has been generally agreed that Bluetooth has a coverage range of between 10 and 100m (Jedwanna and Boonsiripant, 2022; Szyc et al., 2023; Suryavanshi et al., 2019; Jariwala, 2020; GOLIN, 2019; Husain et al., 2019), This coverage distance

is perfect for communication within a modest home or compound premises.

An Arduino is an open-source microcontroller device that may be programmed using a USB cable connected to a computer. It comes in different shapes, sizes, and capabilities. It is an independent system with memory, a processor, and add-ons that can function as embedded systems. It is a low-cost microcontroller that provides an easy way to control hardware using codes. It is suitable for quick prototyping of electronic projects (Akeredolu et al., 2017; Ja'afaru et.al., 2018; Blum, 2019; Jelen, 2021; Shankar et al. 2021; Suraj et al., 2019; Chand and Khosla, 2022; Al-Janabi , 2019). Numerous works have been carried out using the Arduino microcontroller. For example, Iyen et al. (2020) used the Arduino microcontroller together with the rain sensor to construct a rain detector with a rainfall alarm system. The alarm is triggered whenever there is rainfall. Wara and Putri (2021) used an Arduino microcontroller to construct an access control device that is triggered using short message service (SMS). Oladimeji et al. (2020) built a data logger-equipped solar power variable measurement device using an Arduino platform. Their circuit measured five solar parameters, which are voltage, current, light intensity, temperature, and pressure, and saved the data to memory. It has also been applied in robotics (Mohammed Ali et al., 2022; Saw and Mon, 2019).

The Arduino microcontroller has been used as the primary microcontroller unit for quite a lot of home automation projects. For example, Bepery et al. (2019) used Raspberry Pi and Arduino to accomplish internet of things-based home automation. Their system could be connected to the internet and controlled remotely, or it could be controlled locally using a local network. A web-based control interphase was installed on the Raspberry Pi together with an SQL database, which is responsible for storing the states of the devices. Naing and Hlaing (2019) used the GSM module with the RFID module with the Arduino microcontroller together with sensors such as light dependent resistors (LDR), temperature sensors, smoke sensors, and motion sensors to set off alarms,

track and manage lighting, and regulate room temperature. The GSM module was programmed to send automated SMSs to the administrator or home owner as the need arises or in the case of an emergency. David et al. (2015) used an Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller with an embedded microweb server and IP connection to create a flexible and affordable home control and surroundings surveillance solution. This allowed for distant access to and control of the devices. These gadgets were commanded using an online program or a Bluetooth-enabled Android application. The circuit was tested by connecting it to devices such as light switches, socket points, temperature sensors, and motion sensors. Taiwo et al. (2020) suggested a smartphone software platform that was used to monitor and manage household items and gadgets in smart homes. They employed Bluetooth, Arduino, and Zigbee to enable mobile interactions between their home's gadgets. Proteus was used to simulate their task, and they also included a phone application for controlling and inspecting the gadgets or installations. Okorie et al. (2020) constructed a circuit for home automation using analog detectors and a cellular Bluetooth gadget as the basic control mechanisms that are controlled through wireless access to smart phones. A lot of work has also been implemented involving bluetooth and home automation (Amoran et al., 2021; Taiwo et al., 2020; Khin et al., 2019; Shawon et al., 2022; Mustafa et al., 2021; Ngerem et al., 2021; Chioran and Valean, 2020; Okubanjo et al., 2021; Shah and Mahmood, 2020; Islam et al., 2019), nevertheless, the goal of this study is to put into practice an affordable bluetooth and Arduino-based home automation system for academic research, training, and demonstration purposes only. Knowledge of the methodology used in this research may be applied to implement smart home automation and internet of things-based circuits.

The structure of this publication consists of the following: Section 2 delves into the subject of the items and techniques employed in the investigation. In Section 3, we reveal the

outcomes and discuss them. In Section 4, We provide recommendations as we conclude.

Materials And Methods

Materials

The materials used for this research include the Direct Current (D.C.) power supply source, Arduino UNO (as shown in Figure 2), HC-05 Bluetooth module (as shown in Figure 1), breadboard, Resistors 220Ω, soldering lead, jumper wire kit (male and female), capacitor 22pF, variable resistor 10kΩ and light-emitting diodes (LEDs).

Figure 1. A HC-05 Bluetooth Module

Figure 2. An Arduino Microcontroller

Methods

The operation of the proposed circuit is as illustrated in Figure 4, An android application for controlling the devices is downloaded from the Play Store of the Android or Apple phone, or from the marketplace of whatever smart phone is being used. This android application enables the phone to connect to the HC-05 Bluetooth module. The HC-05 Bluetooth module functions by converting the signals received based on the value received from the phone, which is based on the button that is pressed by the phone user. The Arduino sketch is the program that sets different of its terminals to HIGH and LOW depending on the value it receives from the HC-05 Bluetooth module. These states of the output of the Arduino can be used together with transistors and relays to control household electronics and features such as lamps, televisions, sound systems, cooling systems, doors, windows, and so on. However, in this work, the system is tested by switching buzzers and LEDs on and off by pressing values on the application installed on the Bluetooth-enabled mobile phone.

Figure 3. The BlueSPP Android Application Screenshot

While it is possible to write an Android app for a mobile phone using Android Studio, a lot of readily available applications, such as Arduroid, BlueSPP, and Bluetooth Controller, are on the Android Play Store and can be downloaded and used for free. In this research, we made use of the BlueSPP application. A screenshot of the application is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Method of Operation of the Research Work

Table 1. Table Showing the Functioning Parameters of the Circuit

Button	Data	Operation
LED ON	1	LED turned ON
LED OFF	2	LED turned OFF
Buzzer ON	3	Buzzer turned ON
Buzzer OFF	4	Buzzer turned OFF

Results and Discussion

The circuitry for the construction is depicted in Figure 5, the image of the completed unpackaged work is as shown in Figure 6 and the completed and packaged work is as shown in Figure 7. The flowchart for the sketch run in Arduino is as shown in figure 8.

Figure 5. The completed circuit diagram

Figure 6. Construction process

Figure 7. The completed and packaged work

Figure 8. The Flowchart for the Arduino

In this research, the Arduino was programmed to switch a light-emitting diode and a buzzer on and off based on instructions it receives from a HC-05 Bluetooth module connected to it. This circuit can be used for switching heavy gadgets by connecting them through a transistor and relays. It was observed that the circuit could be triggered by the Bluetooth from a smartphone that is up to 100 m away from the circuit; this agrees with the results obtained by other authors who have performed similar research (Bertuletti et al., 2016; Sikora et al., 2018; Araghi et al., 2015; Sollie et al., 2022; Garcla-Ortiz et al., 2021). Figure 9 shows part of the circuit being tested on a breadboard. Table (1) summarizes the working of the final circuit.

Figure 9. Testing the Subcircuits on a Breadboard

Conclusion and Recommendation

We have implemented a wireless, adaptable, and affordable home automation approach in this research. The infrastructure is protected against intrusions or unapproved users. To connect to the home devices, the user must obtain a pairing password for both the Arduino HC-05 Bluetooth and the cell phone.

This strengthens defenses against unapproved access. One can utilize this scheme for any appliance that requires switching on and off within a 100-meter radius of the user without making use of an internet connection. The aim and objectives of the research have been met by constructing a Bluetooth-enabled home automation circuit for demonstration purposes only. The system was constructed and tested within the constraints of available components and instruments. The results of the tests show satisfactory reliability of the various units and the system as a whole.

Future works would consist of hybrid systems that can be controlled locally using the Bluetooth local network and remotely through the internet. Connecting the circuit to relays and transistors will enable it to switch much heavier gadgets. The system can also be joined with sound sensors to trigger switching with claps and motion sensors, which are able to switch devices such as light bulbs when they sense motion in the environment. Also, an LCD (Liquid Crystal

Display) can be added to the circuit to enable display feedback to monitor the status of the circuit independently of monitoring it from the serial monitor on the Arduino IDE displayed on a computer screen.

Conflict of Interest

According to the authors, there are no disclosed conflicts of interest in this work.

References

- Akeredolu, J. B., Wansah, J. F., Omega, H. E., Iseh, A. J., Ocheje, A. J., & Iyen, C. (2017). Development of a low cost automated sliding door. *FUW Trends in Science Technology Journal*, 2(1), 281-289
- Al-Janabi, S. M. A. (2019). *Design and implementing of intelligent anti-theft car security system based on arduino atmega 328p microcontroller*. Master's thesis, Altinbas Universitesi.
- Amoran, A. E., Oluwole, A. S., Fagorola, E. O., and Diarah, R. (2021). Home automated system using bluetooth and an android application. *Scientific African*, 11, e00711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2021.e00711>
- Araghi, B. N., Hammershpj Olesen, J., Krishnan, R., Tprholm Christensen, L., and Lahrmann, H. (2015). Reliability of bluetooth technology for travel time estimation. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 19(3), 240-255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15472450.2013.856727>
- Bepery, C., Baral, S., Khashkel, A., & Hossain, F. (2019). Advanced home automation system using raspberry-pi and arduino. *International journal of computer science and engineering*, 8(2), 1-10.
- Bertuletti, S., Cereatti, A., Caldara, M., Galizzi, M., and Della Croce, U. (2016). Indoor distance estimated from bluetooth low energy signal strength: Comparison of regression models. In *2016 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium (SAS)*, pages 1-5. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SAS.2016.7479899>

- Blum, J. (2019). *Exploring Arduino: tools and techniques for engineering wizardry*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Brahimi, A. (2021). Study and implementation of a home automation and security system. *iKSP Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 1(1).
- Chand, K. & Khosla, A. (2022). Matlab-based real-time data acquisition tool for multimodal biofeedback and arduino-based instruments: Arduino firmata data acquisition (afdaq). *Journal of Information Technology Research (JITR)*, 15(1), 1-20.
- Chioran, D. & Valean, H. (2020). Arduino based smart home automation system. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110410>
- David, N., Chima, A., Ugochukwu, A., and Obinna, E. (2015). Design of a home automation system using arduino. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 6(6), 795-801.
- de Jong, P., Rouwendal, J., & Brouwer, A. (2022). Staying put out of choice or constraint? the residential choice behaviour of dutch older adults. *Population, Space and Place*, 28(4), e2553. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2553>
- Dorve, J., Samarth, M. K., Jais, S. R., Sheikh MdDS, K. P., & Korde, H. (2019). A review on home automation using voice via bluetooth through raspberry pi 3. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 2(3), 332-333.
- Garcia-Ortiz, J. C., Silvestre-Blanes, J., & Sempere-Paya, V. (2021). Experimental application of bluetooth low energy connectionless in smart cities. *Electronics*, 10(22), 2735. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10222735>
- Golin, C. (2019). Implementation and evaluation of a bluetooth low energy indoor navigation system with a passive scanning approach. Retrieved from <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/147320>
- He, S., Zhang, B., Luo, J., & Qu, M. (2021). Research on coexistence and mutual interference of wi-fi and bluetooth. In *2021 International Conference on Microwave and Millimeter Wave Technology (ICMMT)*, pages 1-3. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICMMT52847.2021.9617988>
- Husain, M. I., Alam, M., Rashed, M. G., Haque, M. E., Hasan, M. A. R., & Das, D. (2019). Bluetooth network based remote controlled home automation system. In *2019 1st International conference on advances in science, engineering and robotics technology (ICASERT)*, pages 1-6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASERT.2019.8934500>
- Islam, M. M., Farook, M. N., Mostafa, S., & Arafat, Y. (2019). Design and implementation of an iot based home automation. In *2019 1st international conference on advances in science, engineering and robotics technology (ICASERT)*, pages 1-5. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASERT.2019.8934606>
- Iyen, C., Ayomanor, B., Orume, A., Saleh, S., Jaafaru, S., & Akeredolu, B. J. (2020). Design and construction of a rain detector with an alarm system. *FUW Trends in Science Technology Journal*, 5(3), 686-690
- Ja'afaru, S., Dogara, M. D., Isaac, H. D., Gyuk, P. M., & Iyen, C. (2018). Comparison between a constructed Arduino based system and Keithley Sourcemeter 2400 on some Electronics Devices. *Science World Journal*, 13(2), 55-57. <https://doi.org/10.4314/SWJ.V13I2>
- Jariwala, A. (2020). *Analysis and Test of Bluetooth Communication Systems*. PhD thesis, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Institute.
- Jedwana, K. & Boonsiripant, S. (2022). Evaluation of bluetooth detectors in travel time estimation. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4591. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084591>
- Jelen, B. (2021). Get to know arduino. *XRDS: Crossroads, The ACM Magazine for Students*, 28(1), 62-66. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3481849>

- Juturu, P., Chilakanti, V., & Babu, G. A. (2020). Intelligent bluetooth device to device connection shift. In *2020 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, pages 1-5. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/WCNC45663.2020.9120548>
- Khin, K. W. H., Nwe, K. M., Phway, L. L., & Sann, Z. (2019). Arduinio and bluetooth based smart home control system. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32628/IJSRSET196428>
- Kshirsagar, S., Sachdev, S., Singh, N., Tiwari, A., & Sahu, S. (2020). Iot enabled gesture-controlled home automation for disabled and elderly. In *2020 Fourth International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC)*, pages 821-826. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCMC48092.2020.ICCMC-000152>
- Long, S. L. (2021). *Long distance bluetooth low energy exploitation on a wireless attack platform*. Thesis. Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering.
- Lounis, K. & Zulkernine, M. (2019). Bluetooth low energy makes just works not work. In *2019 3rd cyber security in networking conference (CSNet)*, pages 99-106. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNet47905.2019.9108931>
- Mohammed Ali, H., Hashim, Y., & A AL-Sakkal, G. (2022). Design and implementation of arduino based robotic arm. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 12(2), 1411-1411. <http://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v12i2.pp1411-1418>
- Mustafa, B., Iqbal, M. W., Saeed, M., Shafqat, A. R., Sajjad, H., & Naqvi, M. R. (2021). Iot based low-cost smart home automation system. In *2021 3rd International Congress on Human-Computer Interaction, Optimization and Robotic Applications (HORA)*, pages 1-6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HORA52670.2021.9461276>
- Naing, M. and Hlaing, N. N. S. (2019). Arduino based smart home automation system. *Int. J. Trend Sci. Res. Dev*, 3(4), 276-280. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd23719>
- Ngerem, E., Misra, S., Oluranti, J., Castillo-Beltran, H., Ahuja, R., & Damasevi-cius, R. (2021). A home automation system based on bluetooth technology using an android smartphone. In *Evolving Technologies for Computing, Communication and Smart World: Proceedings of ETCCS 2020*, pages 527-536. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7804-5_40
- Okorie, P., Ibraim, A. A., & Auwal, D. (2020). Design and implementation of an arduino based smart home. In *2020 International Congress on Human-Computer Interaction, Optimization and Robotic Applications (HORA)*, pages 1-6. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/HORA49412.2020.9152922>
- Okubanjo, A., Okandeji, A. A., Abolade, O. R., & Alao, O. (2021). Development of gsm based home automation system using arduino uno microcontroller. *e-ISSN*, 24085162, 599-606.
- Oladimeji, I., Adediji, Y., Akintola, J., Afolayan, M., Ogunbiyi, O., Ibrahim, S., & Olayinka, S. (2020). Design and construction of an arduino-based solar power parameter-measuring system with data logger. *Arid Zone Journal Of Engineering, Technology And Environment*, 16(2), 255-268.
- Oprea, M. & Mocanu, M. (2021). Bluetooth communications in educational robotics. In *2021 23rd International Conference on Control Systems and Computer Science (CSCS)*, pages 408-413. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/CSCS52396.2021.00073>
- Saw, K. K. & Mon, L. Y. (2019). Design and construction of line following robot using arduino. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 3(4), 939-941. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd23977>
- Shah, S. K. A. & Mahmood, W. (2020). Smart home automation using iot and its low cost implementation. *International Journal of Engineering and Manufacturing (IJEM)*, 10(5), 28-36. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijem.2020.05.03>

- Shankar, K., Neelima, N., Naveen, S., & Vardham, B. S. (2021). Design security system based on arduino using motion tracking camera. *J Eng Sci (JES)*, 12(6), 515-521.
- Shawon, M. S. H., Das, C., Ahammed, M. T., Biswas, G., Mia, M. S., Eva, E. A., & Sakib, M. N. (2022). Voice controlled smart home automation system using bluetooth technology. In *2021 4th International Conference on Recent Trends in Computer Science and Technology (ICRTCST)*, pages 67-72. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12928/telkomnika.v20i4.23763>
- Sikora, A., Krzyszton, M., & Marks, M. (2018). Application of bluetooth low energy protocol for communication in mobile networks. In *2018 International Conference on Military Communications and Information Systems (ICMCIS)*, pages 1-6. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMCIS.2018.8398682>
- Sollie, M. L., Gryte, K., Bryne, T. H., & Johansen, T. A. (2022). Outdoor navigation using bluetooth angle-of-arrival measurements. *IEEE Access*, 10, 88012-88033. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3199772>
- Suraj, D., Prasad, V. A., Lokesh, S., Hebbale, S. G., & Salis, V. E. (2019). Obstacle detection for the visually impaired using arduino. In *2019 3rd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, pages 260-265. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOEI.2019.8862635>
- Suryavanshi, N. B., Viswawardhan Reddy, K., & Chandrika, V. R. (2019). Direction finding capability in bluetooth 5.1 standard. In *Ubiquitous Communications and Network Computing: Second EAI International Conference, Bangalore, India, February 8-10, 2019, Proceedings 2*, pages 53-65. Springer. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20615-4_4
- Szyc, K., Nikodem, M., & Zdunek, M. (2023). Bluetooth low energy indoor localization for large industrial areas and limited infrastructure. *Ad Hoc Networks*, 139, 103024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2022.103024>
- Taiwo, O., Ezugwu, A. E., Rana, N., & Abdulhamid, S. M. (2020). Smart home automation system using zigbee, bluetooth and arduino technologies. In *Computational Science and Its Applications-ICCSA 2020: 20th International Conference, Cagliari, Italy, July 1-4, 2020, Proceedings, Part VI 20*, pages 587-597. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58817-5_43
- Turner, A. (2024). How many smartphones are in the world? Retrieved from <https://www.bankmycell.com/blog/how-many-phones-are-in-the-world>
- UNICEF (2023). How many people are there in the world? Retrieved from <https://data.unicef.org/how-many/how-many-people-are-in-the-world/>
- Vijayalakshmi, V. (2021). Iot based home automation using cloud. *Grenze International Journal of Engineering & Technology (GIJET)*, 7(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i2.32.15728>
- Vijayarangam, S., Yadava, A. K., Karthikeyan, G., Suresh, N., Pattanaik, B., & Azahad, S. (2022). A performance improvement in home automation through uncontaminated energy interfaced with multi dimensional machine learning approach. In *2022 International Conference on Edge Computing and Applications (ICECAA)*, pages 1411-1415. IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICECAA55415.2022.9936441>
- Wara, Y. R. & Putri, T. W. O. (2021). Design and construction of additional security device for house door using arduino uno based on short message service. *Journal of Electrical, Electronic, Information, and Communication Technology*, 3(2):67-73. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jeeict.3.2.55481>